

ENDURANCE

Strategies and Services for Enhanced Disruption Resilience and Cooperation

Amid an increasingly interconnected world, the resilience of Europe’s essential services —spanning energy, health, digital services, public administration, and water management (Drinking and Waste) — is vital for societal well-being and economic stability.

The ENDURANCE project addresses the growing complexity of risks such as cyber threats, physical attacks, human errors, and natural disasters. It transcends the focus on individual critical assets by adopting a holistic, pan-European approach to ensuring the continuity of essential services through proactive collaboration and innovation.

3

Year Project Duration

23

Partners across Europe

€5m

EU Horizon Funding

Project Website

Working Group Registration

@ENDURANCE_EU

ENDURANCE PROJECT

@enduranceeu.bsky.social

ENDURANCE PROJECT

PROJECT PARTNERS

Funded by the European Union

The ENDURANCE project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no.101168007.